

ACRIDINE DERIVATIVES AS ANTIMALARIALS. PART II.

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In view of the fact that 5-aminoacridine derivatives generally possess antimalarial activity, several such compounds have been prepared by condensing 2-chloro-7-methoxy-, 2-chloro-7-methyl-, 2:7-dichloro- and 3-nitro-7-methoxy-5-chloro-acridines with 4-aminoantipyrene, 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole and 2-amino-4-methyl-5- β -hydroxyethylthiazole (a ring present in vitamin B₁) respectively. All the compounds are coloured basic substances and form hydrochlorides readily soluble in water. As their molecular weights lie within the limit required for an antimalarial drug, they might be of some therapeutic importance.

Recent researches on the antimalarials point to the fact that for exerting an antimalarial activity the compound must contain a quinoline nucleus (acridine being regarded as a benzoquinoline) and be linked to a chain like dialkylamine, or to a complex like quinuclidine ring. That a mere linking with a chain like the former one, does not help the heterocyclic nucleus in this direction, is again evident from the observations of Slotta and Behnisch (*Ber.*, 1935, 66, 754). It would now be a natural development to make a further study on the influence of other substituents on the above ring systems.

In the present paper certain 5-chloroacridines have been condensed with 4-aminoantipyrene, the dimethyl derivative (pyramidon) of which is known to exert a powerful antipyretic action. The resulting 4-acridyl-aminoantipyrins of the type (I) are generally reddish orange needles being readily soluble in dilute acids. Similarly, in view of the recent observations that vitamin B₁ contains a thiazole nucleus (4-methyl-5- β -hydroxyethylthiazole), the above chloroacridines have been fused with 2-amino-4-methyl-5- β -hydroxyethylthiazole and 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole to afford the corresponding acridylaminothiazoles (II) and (III) respectively. All these acridine derivatives are reddish crystalline substances and form hydrochlorides which are again readily soluble in water. The molecular weight of the compounds varies from about 400—450 and as these figures are found to lie within or near the limit required for an antimalarial drug (*cf.* Slotta and Behnisch, *loc. cit.*), it is being expected that they might be of some therapeutic importance.

(I)

(II)

(III)

where

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-(1'-phenyl-2':3'-dimethyl-5'-pyrazolonyl)-aminoacridine.—2 : 5-Dichloro-7-methoxyacridine was prepared from 5-chloro-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid and 1-phenyl-2 : 3-dimethyl-4-amino-5-pyrazolone which was obtained from antipyrine (cf. D. R. P., 71261). The dichloroacridine and the aminoantipyrine in equal parts were dissolved in phenol and heated on a boiling water-bath for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into caustic soda solution (10%), when a solid separated out. This was filtered and washed free from alkali. On crystallisation from rectified spirit the compound was obtained in microscopic orange-yellow needles, m.p. 248°. (Found: N, 12.57. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4\text{Cl}$ required N, 12.77 per cent). It is easily soluble in dilute acids and is reprecipitated on dilution with alkali.

2-Chloro-7-methyl-5-(1'-phenyl-2':3'-dimethyl-5'-pyrazolonyl)-aminoacridine.—The 5-chloroacridine derivative obtained from 5-chloro-4'-methyl-diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid, was condensed with 4-aminoantipyrine as in the previous case. The solid isolated was crystallised from rectified spirit in orange microscopic needles, m.p. 257°. (Found: N, 13.17. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{21}\text{ON}_4\text{Cl}$ requires N, 13.07 per cent).

3-Nitro-7-methoxy-5-(1'-phenyl-2':3'-dimethyl-5'-pyrazolonyl)-aminoacridine.—3-Nitro-7-methoxy-5-chloroacridine (m.p. 223°) obtained from 4-nitro-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid, and 4-aminoantipyrine gave under the usual conditions a deep red product which on crystallisation from rectified spirit melted at 278-79°. (Found: N, 15.01. $C_{20}H_{21}O_4N_6$ requires N, 15.38 per cent).

2 : 5 : 7-Trichloroacridine.—2 : 5 : 7-Trichloroacridine, obtained from 4' : 5-dichlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid, and the aminoantipyrine in equal proportions were heated together in presence of phenol for about 3 hours on a boiling water-bath. On cooling the mixture was diluted with ether when the hydrochloride of the condensation product separated out. This was filtered, washed with ether and finally treated with dilute ammonia. The residual mass was crystallised from dilute alcohol (1 : 1) and obtained in fine reddish needles, m.p. 276-77° (decomp.). (Found: N, 12.69. $C_{24}H_{18}ON_4Cl_2$ requires N, 12.47 per cent).

2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-(4'-phenylthiazolyl)-aminoacridine.—2 : 5-Dichloro-7-methoxy-acridine was dissolved in phenol on a boiling water-bath and treated with an equimolecular quantity of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (prepared from ω -bromoacetophenone and thiourea). The mixture was heated for more than 3 hours, when it was cooled and diluted with ether with stirring. A solid separated out which was collected, washed with ether and then triturated with dilute ammonia. The residual mass was filtered, washed with water and purified by repeated crystallisation from rectified spirit. (Found: Cl, 8.22. $C_{23}H_{16}ON_3ClS$ requires Cl, 8.5 per cent). It is a dark red crystalline substance, m.p. 246°-47° and is readily soluble in dilute acids.

2-Chloro-7-methyl-5-(4'-phenylthiazolyl)-aminoacridine.—Equimolecular quantities of 2 : 5-dichloro-7-methylacridine and 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole were heated in presence of phenol on an oil-bath at 120° for 3 hours. The reaction mixture on subsequent treatment as in the previous case afforded a red crystalline substance which separated from dilute alcohol (1 : 1) in fine microscopic needles, m.p. 263-64°. (Found: Cl, 8.97. $C_{23}H_{16}N_3ClS$ requires Cl, 8.84 per cent).

2:5:7-Trichloro-5-(4'-phenylthiazolyl)-aminoacridine.—2:5:7-Trichloroacridine and the aminophenylthiazole in molecular proportions were dissolved in phenol by warming and subsequently heated in on oil-bath at 120° for about 3 hours. The usual treatment of the reaction mixture yielded the condensation product which was subsequently crystallised from alcohol in

reddish needles, m.p. 269-70°. (Found: Cl, 16.97. $C_{22}H_{12}N_2ClS_2$ requires Cl, 16.82 per cent).

3-Nitro-7-methoxy-5-(4'-phenylthiazolyl)-aminoacridine.—3-Nitro-5-chloro-7-methoxyacridine was dissolved in phenol by heating on a water-bath. To the solution an equimolecular quantity of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole was gradually added and the mixture was finally heated to 110-120° for about 3 hours on an oil-bath. After cooling, it was poured into caustic soda solution (10%) and the precipitate obtained was filtered and washed with water. It was then crystallised from alcohol in fine reddish needles, m. p. 264-65°. (Found: N, 12.88. $C_{22}H_{14}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 13.08 per cent).

2-Amino-4-methyl-5-β-hydroxyethylthiazole.—γ-Aceto-γ-chloropropyl alcohol (9 g.) was mixed with thiourea (6 g.) and absolute alcohol (30 c. c.) in a stoppered flask and left over at the room temperature (28°) for 2 days. A further quantity (3 g.) of thiourea was added and the mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 1 hour. Alcohol was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the residual mass was diluted with water when a clear solution was obtained. On saturating the solution with potassium carbonate an oily layer separated out. This was collected and directly distilled in *vacuo*. A yellow viscous liquid (3 g.) distilling at 200°/7 mm. was collected. It was dissolved in anhydrous ether and the ethereal solution was treated with dry hydrogen chloride. The hydrochloride separated out and was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether and dried over sulphuric acid in *vacuo*, m.p. 138°. (Found: N, 14.13; Cl, 18.05. $C_6H_{10}ON_2S$, HCl requires N, 14.4; Cl, 18.25 per cent). The free base is moderately soluble in water and on long standing sets to a solid mass, m. p. 70°.

2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-(4'-methyl-5'-β-hydroxyethylthiazolyl)-aminoacridine.—2:5-Dichloro-7-methoxyacridine (1 part) and 2-amino-4-methyl-5-β-hydroxyethylthiazole (1 part) in phenolic solution were heated together at 110-120° for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was poured over dilute caustic soda solution (10%) without allowing the temperature to rise. The solid was collected, dissolved in dilute acetic acid and filtered. The filtrate was made alkaline with dilute ammonia in cold when the acridine base separated out. This was collected, washed and crystallised from alcohol and water (1:2). (Found: Cl, 8.69. $C_{20}H_{18}O_2N_2ClS$ requires Cl, 8.88 per cent). It is a fine orange coloured solid, m.p. 256° (decomp.), soluble in common organic solvents and readily soluble in acids.

2-Chloro-7-methyl-5-(4'-methyl-5'-β-hydroxyethylthiazolyl)-aminoacridine.—2:5-Dichloro-7-methylacridine and the above thiazole in equal parts were heated in presence of phenol as usual. The reaction mixture was

poured into dilute caustic soda solution and the solid separating on being washed with water was crystallised from rectified spirit, m. p. 254°. (Found : Cl, 9.06. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_2$ ClS requires Cl, 9.25 per cent).

2 : 7-Dichloro-5- (4'-methyl-5'- β -hydroxyethylthiazoyl) - aminoacridine.—2:5:7-Trichloroacridine and the thiazole afforded the condensation product under the usual conditions. It was crystallised from alcohol in fine orange microscopic needles, m.p. 273°. (Found : Cl, 17.44. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_2$ Cl₂S requires Cl, 17.58 per cent).

3-Nitro-7-methoxy-5- (4'-methyl-5'- β -hydroxyethylthiazoyl) - aminoacridine.—Equal quantities of 3-nitro-7-methoxy-5-chloroacridine and the hydroxyethylthiazole were heated together as in the previous cases, and the reaction mixture on usual treatment afforded the aminoacridine derivative. On crystallisation from rectified spirit it was obtained in reddish needles, m. p. 261-62° (decomp.). (Found : N, 13.96. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4N_4S$ requires N, 13.65 per cent).

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Received March 4, 1938.